

TURLI XIL STRESS OMILLARDAN GARMSEL OMILINING G'O'ZA BARG SATHIGA TA'SIRI

Ostonova Gulnoza Rashidovna

Osiyo xalqaro universiteti o'qituvchisi
Email: ostonovagulnozarashidovna@oxu.uz
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10159192>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 10-November 2023 yil
Ma'qullandi: 15- November 2023 yil
Nashr qilindi: 20-November 2023 yil

KEY WORDS

Buxoro-8 g'o'za navi, Buxoro-10 g'o'za navi, barg sathi, garmsell.

ABSTRACT

Mazkur maqolada, laboratoriya sharoitida g'o'za o'simligining Buxoro-8 va Buxoro-10 navlarida barg sathining o'zgarishiga garmsel (issiq shamol) omilining ta'siri aniqlandi. Tadqiqot Buxoro-8 va Buxoro-10 navlarining turli vegetatsiya davrlarida olib borildi. Natijada, vegetatsiya oxirida Buxoro-8 va Buxoro-10 navlaridagi variantlarda barg sathi mos ravishda: 2425 sm²; 2778sm² ni tashkil etganligi aniqlandi.

Dunyo miqyosida kuzatilayotgan global iqlim o'zgarishlar ya'ni biosferada havo haroratining oshishi, nisbiy namlikning keskin pasayishi, parnik effektining yuzaga kelishi va boshqa sabablar qishloq xo'jaligidagi ekin mahsulotlarini yetishtirishda bir qancha qiyinchiliklarni keltirib chiqarmoqda.

Buxoro viloyatining o'tloqi-allyuvial tuproqlardagi sho'rlanish, havoning quruq va juda issiq bo'lganligi, yog'ingarchilik miqdorining kam bo'lishi, o'simliklarda tranpiratsiya jarayonining yuqori bo'lishi sababli qishloq xo'jaligida yetishtiriladigan ekinlar ko'p bora sug'orishni talab etmoqda. Issiq va quruq shamol (garmsel) iyun oyining oxiri va iyulning boshlarida yuzaga kelib, bu davr ko'pincha qishloq xo'jalik ekinlarining gullash bosqichiga to'g'ri keladi.

O'simlik ildizi garmsel vaqtida tuproqdagi suvni o'zlashtirishi bilanoq tanasidan ko'p miqdorda suv bug'lanadi [1]. Bu kritik faza o'simliklarning gullash davriga to'g'ri kelsa, o'simliklarda hosil elementlarning to'kilib nobud bo'lishiga olib keladi. Natijada, hosildorlik ko'rsatkichining pasayishiga olib keladi [2]. Shu sababdan, bunday noqulay stress omillar ta'siriga chidamli bo'lgan g'o'za navlarini yetishtirish dolzarb masalalardan biri sanaladi.

Tadqiqot obyekti sifatida Buxoro viloyati hududida yetishtiriladigan Buxoro-8 va Buxoro-10 g'o'za navi tanlab olindi. Tajriba Buxoro davlat universiteti Botanika va o'simliklar fiziologiyasi kafedrasining laboratoriyasida sun'iy ravishda hosil qilingan issiq shamol (garmsell)ning Buxoro-8 va Buxoro-10 g'o'za navlaridagi barg sathiga ta'siri aniqlandi va nazorat (stress omil ta'sir ettirilmagan) variantlari bilan solishtirib o'rganildi. Tajriba 4 qaytiriqda, 3 marta o'tkazildi. G'o'za turli vegetatsiya davrlarida garmsellning barg sathiga ta'siri N.N. Tretyakov usuli orqali aniqlandi[3]. Bunda variantlar kesimi bo'yicha g'o'zaning turli o'suv fazalarida mos ravishda: 25-10-

10 va 3 donadan iborat o'simlik namunalardan olingan barglar millimetrli qog'ozda yuzasi (sm^2) hisoblanib, o'rtachasi aniqlandi.

Olingan tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra, 2-4 chinbarglik davrda birinchi variantdan to'rtinchi variantgacha barg sathining o'rtacha miqdori mos ravishda: 390 sm^2 , 375 sm^2 ; 415 sm^2 ; 395 sm^2 ni tashkil etdi. Eng ijobiy natija Nazorat-2 variantda kuzatilib, Nazorat -1 variantga nisbatan barg sathi 25 sm^2 ortiq ekanligi aniqlandi (1-jadval).

1-jadval

Turli xil stress omillardan garmsellning g'o'za barg sathiga ta'siri

T/r	Variantlar	G'o'zaning turli vegetatsiya davrlarida barg sathi ko'rsatkichlari, sm^2			
		2-4 chinbarglik	Shonalash	Gullash	Pishish
1	Nazorat -1	390	1605	1815	2508
2	Buxoro-8	375	1570	1745	2425
3	Nazorat-2	415	1704	2015	2604
4	Buxoro-10	395	1678	1955	2778

Shonalash davrida barg sathi bo'yicha olib borilgan tadqiqot natijalari tahlil qilinganda, Nazorat-1, Buxoro-8, Nazorat-2, Buxoro-10 variantlar kesimida barg sathi mos ravishda: 1605 sm^2 , 1570 sm^2 , 1704 sm^2 , 1678 sm^2 ni tashkil etishi aniqlandi. Tajriba variantlari ichida eng ijobiy variant, Nazorat-2 variantida kuzatilib, qolgan variantlarga nisbatan mos ravishda: 99 sm^2 , 134 sm^2 , 26 sm^2 barg sathi ortiq ekanligi aniqlandi.

Gullash davrida olib borilgan tajriba natijalariga ko'ra, Nazorat-1, Buxoro-8, Nazorat-2, Buxoro-10 variantlarda mos ravishda: 1815 sm^2 ; 1745 sm^2 ; 2015 sm^2 ; 1955 sm^2 ni tashkil etdi. G'o'za vegetatsiyasining oxirida ya'ni pishish fazasida Nazorat-1, Buxoro-8, Nazorat-2, Buxoro-10 variantlarda barg sathi aniqlanganda, eng ijobiy natija Nazorat-2 va Buxoro-10 g'o'za navlarida kuzatildi.

Yuqorida keltirilgan natijalar asosida quyidagicha xulosalar qilish mumkin: garmsel omili barg hujayralarining o'sishi, rivojlanishini amalga oshiruvchi apikal va interkalyar meristema hujayralarining faolliyatini sekinlashtiradi. Shu boisdan, barg sathi tajriba variantlarida nazoratga nisbatan sezilarli darajada kamayganligi aniqlandi.

Fotosintez jarayoni bargdagi xlorofill donachalarida amalga oshadi. Bargning rangi to'q yashil va sathining katta bo'lishi fotosintez jarayonining jadalligini hamda xo'jalik va biologik hosilning yuqori bo'lishini ta'minlaydi [4] [5].

Buxoro viloyati sharoitida tez-tez kuzatiladigan stressor omillardan garmsellning esishi fiziologik nuqtai nazardan paxta maydonlarida yuqori va sifatli hosil olishda Buxoro-10 g'o'za navini ekish maqsadga muvofiqdir.

Adabiyotlar:

1. Xo'jayev J. O'simliklar fiziologiyasi Farg'ona: 2021. – 6. 56-73.
2. Шевякова Н И Состояние и новые подходы к решению проблемы соли устойчивости растений. Сб « Проблемы соли устойчивости растений» Т. 1989. С 95-112..
3. Физиология и биохимия сельскохозяйственных растений / под ред. Н.Н. Третьякова. –Москва: Колос, 2000. -6.225-435..][Храмченкова О.М. Практикум по физиологии растений. Гомель: Гомель Государственное Университет, 2017. – С. 38-40.

4. Икрамова М.Л., Батталов А.М. Перспективный сорт хлопчатника “Бухоро -10”// Заявка на участие Круглый стол «Формирование и развитие сельскохозяйственной науки в XXI веке», Астраханская область, Черноярский район, с Соленое Займище, Россия, 2016. –С. 119-122.
5. Ikromova M.L. Paxtachilik va Buxoro g'oz'a navlarining o'ziga xos yetishtirish agrotekhnologiyasi. Buxoro. Durдона, 2020. - 38 b.
6. Ostonova, G. (2023). ICHKI SEKRETSIYA BEZLARI FIZIOLOGIYASI. Центральноеазиатский журнал образования и инноваций, 2(10 Part 3), 110-115.
7. Yomgirovna, R. G. (2023). AGROBIOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF BENTONITE IN AGRICULTURE. TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI, 3(9), 126-130.
8. Rakhimovna, T. D., & Yomgirovna, R. G. (2023). AGROBIOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF BENTONITE IN AGRICULTURE. Conferencea, 9-14.
9. Rahimova, G. (2023). MAKTABLARDA BIOLOGIYA FANINI O'QITISHDA ZAMONAVIY INTERFAOL METODLARDAN FOYDALANISH. В CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF EDUCATION AND INNOVATION (Т. 2, Выпуск 10, сс. 103–109).Zenodo.
10. Qobilovna, A. M. (2023). COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE AS A FACTOR OF TEACHER'S PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCY. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 3(09), 32-44.
11. Ataulayeva, M. (2023). COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE AS A FACTOR OF PERSONAL AND PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF A FUTURE SPECIALIST. International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research, 3(10), 109-114.
12. Qobilovna, A. M. (2021). BOSHLANG 'ICH SINFI O 'QITUVCHILARIDA KOMMUNIKATIV KOMPITENTLIK SHAKLLANISHINING IJTIMOIIY-PSIXOLOGIK DETERMINANTLARI. Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS), (Special Issue), 102-105.
13. Narzulyeva, U., & Ismoilova, N. (2023). DETECTION OF EATING BEHAVIOR DISORDERS IN STUDENTS BEFORE THE EXAM USING THE DEBQ QUESTIONNAIRE. Наука и инновация, 1(15), 112-114.
14. Narzulaeva, U. (2023). PATHOGENETIC MECHANISMS OF MICROCIRCULATION DISORDERS. International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research, 3(10), 60–65. Retrieved from <https://researchcitations.com/index.php/ibmscr/article/view/2811>
15. Нарзуллаева, У. Р., Самиева, Г. У., & Пардаева, З. С. (2020). Pathogenetic aspects of verified risk factors such as arterial hypertension and dyslipidemia in the development of chronic heart failure. American Journal of Medicine and Medical Sciences, 10(10), 776-779.
16. Narzulaeva Umida Rakhmatulloevna, Samieva Gulnoza Utkurovna, & Ismatova Marguba Shaukatovna (2020). SPECIFICITY OF THE CLINICAL COURSE OF THE INITIAL STAGES OF HYPERTENSION IN ARID ZONES OF UZBEKISTAN AND NON-DRUG APPROACHES TO TREATMENT. Кронос, (4 (43)), 15-17.
17. Umida Raxmatulloevna Narzulaeva, & Mohigul Abdurasulovna Bekkulova (2023). Arterial gipertenziya etiologiyasida dislipidemiyaning xavf omili sifatidagi roli. Science and Education, 4 (2), 415-419.
18. Narzulaeva, U. R., & Samieva, G. U. (2021). Nasirova ShSh. Hemoreological Disorders in The Early Stages Of Hypertension In Hot Climates. Journal of Biomedicine and Practice, 6(1), 221-225.
19. Axmedova, M. (2023). THE IMPACT OF SOCIOCULTURAL FACTORS ON THE

- PERVASIVENESS OF DENTAL CARIES AS A COMPLEX HEALTH CONDITION IN CONTEMPORARY SOCIETY. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 3(9), 24-28.
20. Ostonova, G. (2023). ICHKI SEKRETSIYA BEZLARI FIZIOLOGIYASI. *Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций*, 2(10 Part 3), 110-115.
21. Yomgirovnova, R. G. (2023). AGROBIOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF BENTONITE IN AGRICULTURE. *TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 3(9), 126-130.
22. Rakhimovna, T. D., & Yomgirovnova, R. G. (2023). AGROBIOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF BENTONITE IN AGRICULTURE. *Conferencea*, 9-14.
23. Rahimova, G. (2023). МАКТАБЛАРДА BIOLOGIYA FANINI O'QITISHDA ZAMONAVIY INTERFAOL METODLARDAN FOYDALANISH. В *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF EDUCATION AND INNOVATION* (Т. 2, Выпуск 10, сс. 103–109).Zenodo.
24. Djalilova, Z. (2023). THE USE OF LATIN TERMINOLOGY IN MEDICAL CASE. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 2(14), 9-15.
25. Obidovna, D. Z., & Sulaymonovich, D. S. (2023). Forming a Healthy Lifestyle for Students on the Example of the Volleyball Section in Universities. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 3(3), 22-25.
26. Obidovna, D. Z., & Sulaymonovich, D. S. (2022). Physical activity and its impact on human health and longevity. *Достижения науки и образования*, (2 (82)), 120-126.
27. Obidovna, D. Z., & Sulaymonovich, D. S. (2022). THE CONCEPT OF "HEALTHY LIFESTYLE" IN PSYCHOLOGICAL RESEARCH. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 3(06), 53-64.
28. 24. Musayeva, A. (2023). MADANIYATSHUNOSLIK YONDASHUVI ASOSIDA TALABA-YOSHLARNING KOMMUNIKATIV KOMPETENSIYALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH. *Science and innovation*, 2(Special Issue 9), 97-99.
29. 25. Караматовна, М. А. (2023). ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ В ЯЗЫКОЗНАНИИ ТЕОРИИ СЕМАНТИЧЕСКОГО ПОЛЯ. Мусаева, А. (2023). РУССКИЙ ЯЗЫК В МЕЖКУЛЬТУРНОЙ СРЕДЕ. *Современная наука и исследования*, 2 (4), 182–186.
30. 26. Мусаева, А (2023). РУССКИЙ ЯЗЫК В МЕЖКУЛЬТУРНОЙ СРЕДЕ. *Современная наука и исследования*, 2(4), 182-186 <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/19208>
31. Narzulyeva, U., & Ismoilova, N. (2023). DETECTION OF EATING BEHAVIOR DISORDERS IN STUDENTS BEFORE THE EXAM USING THE DEBQ QUESTIONNAIRE. *Наука и инновация*, 1(15), 112-114.
32. Narzulaeva, U. (2023). PATHOGENETIC MECHANISMS OF MICROCIRCULATION DISORDERS. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 3(10), 60–65. Retrieved from <https://researchcitations.com/index.php/ibmscr/article/view/2811>
33. Kholliyev, A., & Boltayeva, Z. (2020). Resistance of cotton varieties to water deficiency. *Збірник наукових праць Л'ОГОС*, 70-72.
34. Холлиев, А., Махмудова, Ш., & Иргашева, Н. (2019). Меры борьбы против зерновок на зернобобовых культурах. *НАУКА, ПРОИЗВОДСТВО, БИЗНЕС*, 192.
35. Kholliyev, A., Boltayeva, Z., & Norboyeva, U. (2020). Cotton water exchange in water deficiency. *Збірник наукових праць Л'ОГОС*, 54-56.
36. Ergashovich, K. A., & Akmalovna, A. C. (2022). Soybean Cultivation Technology and

Basics of Land Preparation for Planting. Eurasian Journal of Research, Development and Innovation, 7, 8-13

37. Kazakova, N. N., & Sh, S. D. (2022). Evaluation of the prevalence and intensity of caries in children with rheumatism. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876, 16(5), 156-160.

38. Rasulov, Z. I. (2023). THE NOTION OF NON-EQUIVALENT WORDS AND REALIAS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities, 11(6), 35-40.

39. Rasulov, Z. (2023). LISONIY TEJAMKORLIKNING AXBOROT IFODASIDAGI ORTIQCHALIKKA MUNOSABATI. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.uz), 42(42).

40. Togaydullaeva, D. D. (2022). ARTERIAL GIPERTONIYA BOR BEMORLARDA KOMORBIDLIK UCHRASHI. TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 2(11), 32-35.

41. Togaydullaeva, D. D. (2022). Eraklarda yurak ishemik kasalligining kechishida metabolik sindrom komponentlarining ta'siri. Fan, ta'lim, madaniyat va innovatsiya, 1(4), 29-34.

42. Gafurovna, A. N., Xalimovich, M. N., & Komilovich, E. B. Z. (2023). KLIMAKTERIK YOSHDAGI AYOLLARDA ARTERIAL GIPERTENZIYANING KECHISHI. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 23(6), 26-31.

INNOVATIVE
ACADEMY